

ABOUT MODERN DRUGS FOR THE TREATMENT OF ALZHEIMER'S

SOPHIO BRUNJADZE

Faculty of Natural Sciences and Health Care of Batumi Shota Rustaveli State University,
Batumi, Georgia

Abstract. *Alzheimer's disease is a type of dementia that affects memory, thinking and behavior. Symptoms eventually grow severe enough to interfere with daily tasks.*

The treatment will allow people to have more time to participate in daily life and live independently two treatments — donanemab (Kisunla™) and lecanemab (Leqembi®) — demonstrate that removing beta-amyloid, one of the hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease, from the brain reduces cognitive and functional decline in people living with early Alzheimer's. Other treatments can temporarily slow the worsening of dementia symptoms and improve quality of life for those with living Alzheimer's and their caregivers. Today, there is a worldwide effort underway to find better ways to treat the disease, delay its onset and prevent it from developing. is critical to ensure that the person living with dementia receives the best possible care.

They work differently by targeting beta-amyloid at different stages of plaque formation, and ultimately these treatments lower beta-amyloid to slow progression of the disease and to reduce clinical decline.

Keywords: *Alzheimer's disease, donanemab (Kisunla™) , lecanemab (Leqembi®)*

Alzheimer's disease is a type of dementia that affects memory, thinking and behavior. Symptoms eventually grow severe enough to interfere with daily tasks.1.2.3.4.

The treatment will allow people to have more time to participate in daily life and live independently. Individuals should talk with their health care provider to develop an Alzheimer's treatment plan that is right for them, including weighing the benefits and risks of all approved medications and therapies.

Alzheimer's is the most common cause of dementia, a general term for memory loss and other cognitive abilities serious enough to interfere with daily life. Alzheimer's disease accounts for 60-80% of dementia cases.

Alzheimer's is a progressive disease, where dementia symptoms gradually worsen over a number of years. In its early stages, memory loss is mild, but with late-stage Alzheimer's, individuals lose the ability to carry on a conversation and respond to their environment. On average, a person with Alzheimer's lives four to eight years after diagnosis but can live as long as 20 years, depending on other factors.2.3.4.5.6.

two treatments — donanemab (Kisunla™) and lecanemab (Leqembi®) — demonstrate that removing beta-amyloid, one of the hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease, from the brain reduces cognitive and functional decline in people living with early Alzheimer's. Other treatments can temporarily slow the worsening of dementia symptoms and improve quality of life for those with living Alzheimer's and their caregivers. Today, there is a worldwide effort underway to find better ways to treat the disease, delay its onset and prevent it from developing. is critical to ensure that the person living with dementia receives the best possible care.

That donanemab is appropriate for people living with early symptomatic Alzheimer's disease, which includes mild cognitive impairment and the mild dementia stage of Alzheimer's disease, with confirmed amyloid plaques. The treatment was studied in people living with mild Alzheimer's dementia and MCI due to Alzheimer's who showed evidence of a buildup of beta-amyloid plaques in the brain.

The therapy has not been tested on people with more advanced stages of Alzheimer's or those without clinical symptoms. There is no evidence to date that this or any treatment can restore or reverse memory loss or cognitive function due to Alzheimer's disease. There is no single diagnostic test that can determine if a person is living with Alzheimer's. Physicians

use a variety of approaches and tools to help make a diagnosis. To diagnose Alzheimer's, physicians may use medical history, mental status tests, physical and neurological exams, biofluid (CSF and blood) tests and brain imaging. The FDA does not specify a diagnostic tool to determine elevated beta-amyloid, but tools such as an amyloid PET. Some people have a genetic risk factor (ApoE ϵ 4 gene carriers) that may cause an increased risk for the side effect of amyloid-related imaging abnormalities (ARIA). The FDA encourages that testing for ApoE ϵ 4 status should be performed prior to initiation of treatment to inform the risk of developing ARIA. In a news release, the manufacturers of donanemab announced they are setting the price of the drug at \$32,000 a year. Different from the first two approved therapies in this class, this drug was tested so that treatment was stopped once plaques were cleared from the brain. The cost of the treatment will vary based on patient and length of treatment.

The treatment is administered every four weeks through an IV, lasting about 30 minutes for each infusion. Typically, infusions can be done at hospitals and infusion therapy centers.

Lecanemab (Leqembi®) is an antibody intravenous (IV) infusion therapy that targets and removes beta-amyloid from the brain. It has received traditional approval from the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) to treat early Alzheimer's disease, including people living with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or mild dementia due to Alzheimer's disease who have confirmation of elevated beta-amyloid in the brain. Leqembi lowers beta-amyloid in the brain and reduces cognitive and functional decline in people living with early Alzheimer's. On Jan. 26, 2025, the FDA approved once every four weeks maintenance dosing of lecanemab for early Alzheimer's disease. Patients who have completed their initial regimen (around 18 months) of lecanemab infusions every two weeks may now be able to transition to a regimen of one infusion every four weeks to sustain the clearance of amyloid from the brain. This decision will need to be made in consultation with their clinician. This less-frequent dosing should be less burdensome and easier for patients and care partners to continue long-term.

While monoclonal antibodies like lecanemab that target beta-amyloid in the brain belong to the same class of treatments, no treatments are the same. They work differently by targeting beta-amyloid at different stages of plaque formation, and ultimately these treatments lower beta-amyloid to slow progression of the disease and to reduce clinical decline.

REFERENCES

1. Alexander M, Kulminski, Ethan Jain-Washburn, Elena Loiko, Yury Loika, Fan Feng, Irina Culminkaya, Associations of the APOE ϵ 2 and ϵ 4 alleles and polygenic profiles comprising APOE-TOMM40-APOC1 variants with Alzheimer's disease biomarkers, *Aging*, 10.18632/aging.204384, **14**, 24, (9782-9804), (2022).
2. *Vashadze SH* About Dementia J. Experimental and Clinical Medicine, 2017, 4, pp.75-77http://www.jecm.ge/summary2017_4.htm
3. Vashadze Shorena, Kekenadze Mariam, Brunjadze Sophio, Chikhradze Ana, Katamadze Shorena, Kajaia Medea Characteristics of dementia in patients with diabetes mellitus **The journal Emergency Medicine (Ukraine)** Том 18, № 1, 2022DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22141/2224-0586.18.1.2022.1463>
4. Kwangsik N, Kueider-Paisley A, Dehkordib SM, et al. Altered bile acid profile in mild cognitive impairment and Alzheimer's disease: relationship to neuroimaging and CSF biomarkers. *Alzheimer's Dement.* 2019; **15**: 232-244.
5. Zhu B, Wang RM, Wang JT, Chen RL, Zheng YF, Zhang L, Zhao ZG. Metab. Correlation of rs9331888 polymorphism with Alzheimer's disease among Caucasian and Chinese populations: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Brain Dis.* 2017 Aug;32(4):981-989. doi: 10.1007/s11011-017-9957-8. Epub 2017 Feb 6. PMID: 28168383
6. Zhao N, Liu CC, Qiao W, Bu G. Apolipoprotein E, receptors, and modulation of Alzheimer's disease. *Biol Psychiatry.* 2018; **83**: 347-357.